

Study of the Fractional Differential Problem of Some Matrix Fractional Functions

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Abstract: In this paper, based on Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we can obtain arbitrary order fractional derivative of two types of matrix fractional functions by using some methods. In fact, our results are generalizations of ordinary calculus results.

Keywords: Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative, new multiplication, fractional analytic functions, matrix fractional functions.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the second half of the 20th century, a considerable number of studies on fractional calculus were published in the engineering literature. In fact, fractional calculus has many applications in physics, mechanics, biology, electrical engineering, viscoelasticity, control theory, economics, and other fields [1-17]. There is no doubt that fractional calculus has become an exciting new mathematical method to solve diverse problems in mathematics, science, and engineering.

Until now, the rules of fractional derivative are not unique. Many authors have given the definition of fractional derivative. The commonly used definition is the Riemann-Liouville (R-L) definition. Other useful definitions include Caputo definition of fractional derivative, Grunwald Letnikov (G-L) fractional derivative, conformable fractional derivative, and Jumarie's modified R-L fractional derivative [18-22]. Since Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative helps to avoid non-zero fractional derivative of constant function, it is easier to use this definition to connect fractional calculus with traditional calculus.

In this paper, based on Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we study the fractional differential problem of the following two types matrix fractional functions:

$$\begin{aligned} & \cos_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{Ln}_{\alpha}(1 + 2r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2) \\ & - \sin_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \arctan_{\alpha} \left(r \sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-1)} \right), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \cos_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \arctan_{\alpha} \left(r \sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-1)} \right) \\ & + \sin_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{Ln}_{\alpha}(1 + 2r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2), \end{aligned}$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, r is a real number, $|r| < 1$, p is a positive integer, and A is a real matrix. Using some methods, we can evaluate arbitrary order fractional derivative of these two types of matrix fractional functions. Moreover, our results are generalizations of traditional calculus results.

II. PRELIMINARIES

At first, we introduce the fractional derivative used in this paper and its properties.

Definition 2.1 ([23]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. The Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) α -fractional derivative is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)-f(x_0)}{(x-t)^\alpha} dt, \quad (1)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function. On the other hand, for any positive integer m , we define $({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)^m[f(x)] = ({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha) \cdots ({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[f(x)]$, the m -th order α -fractional derivative of $f(x)$.

Proposition 2.2 ([24]): If α, β, x_0, C are real numbers and $\beta \geq \alpha > 0$, then

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[(x-x_0)^\beta] = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta-\alpha+1)}(x-x_0)^{\beta-\alpha}, \quad (2)$$

and

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[C] = 0. \quad (3)$$

Definition 2.3 ([25]): If x, x_0 , and a_n are real numbers for all n , $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as an α -fractional power series, that is, $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x-x_0)^{n\alpha}$ on some open interval containing x_0 , then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is α -fractional analytic at x_0 . Furthermore, if $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is continuous on closed interval $[a, b]$ and it is α -fractional analytic at every point in open interval (a, b) , then f_α is called an α -fractional analytic function on $[a, b]$.

In the following, we introduce a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions.

Definition 2.4 ([26]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Assume that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional power series at $x = x_0$,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x-x_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad (4)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x-x_0)^{n\alpha}. \quad (5)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x-x_0)^{n\alpha} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x-x_0)^{n\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Definition 2.5 ([27]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x is a real number. The α -fractional exponential function is defined by

$$E_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (8)$$

On the other hand, the α -fractional cosine and sine function are defined as follows:

$$\cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{2n\alpha}}{\Gamma(2n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2n}, \quad (9)$$

and

$$\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{(2n+1)\alpha}}{\Gamma((2n+1)\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (2n+1)}. \quad (10)$$

Definition 2.6 ([28]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and A is a matrix. The matrix α -fractional exponential function is defined by

$$E_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A^n \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(A \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} n}. \quad (11)$$

And the matrix α -fractional cosine and sine function are defined as follows:

$$\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A^n \frac{(-1)^n x^{2n\alpha}}{\Gamma(2n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} \left(A \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2n}, \quad (12)$$

and

$$\sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A^n \frac{(-1)^n x^{(2n+1)\alpha}}{\Gamma((2n+1)\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} \left(A \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (2n+1)}. \quad (13)$$

Theorem 2.7 (matrix fractional Euler's formula): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and A is a real matrix, then

$$E_{\alpha}(iAx^{\alpha}) = \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + i\sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}). \quad (14)$$

Theorem 2.8 (matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, p is an integer, and A is a real matrix, then

$$[\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + i\sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} p} = \cos_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) + i\sin_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}). \quad (15)$$

Definition 2.9: The smallest positive real number T_{α} such that $E_{\alpha}(iT_{\alpha}) = 1$, is called the period of $E_{\alpha}(ix^{\alpha})$.

III. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we obtain arbitrary order fractional derivative of two types of matrix fractional functions by using some techniques. At first, two lemmas are needed.

Lemma 3.1: Suppose that $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, r is a real number, and A is a real matrix, then

$$Ln_{\alpha}(1 + rE_{\alpha}(iAx^{\alpha})) = \frac{1}{2} Ln_{\alpha}(1 + 2r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2) + i \cdot \arctan_{\alpha} \left(r\sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-1)} \right). \quad (16)$$

Proof $Ln_{\alpha}(1 + rE_{\alpha}(iAx^{\alpha}))$

$$= Ln_{\alpha}(1 + r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + i\sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})) \quad (\text{by matrix fractional Euler's formula})$$

$$= Ln_{\alpha} \left(\otimes_{\alpha} \left[(1 + r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + 2r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2]^{\otimes_{\alpha} -1/2} + i\sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + 2r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2]^{\otimes_{\alpha} -1/2} \right] \right)$$

$$= Ln_{\alpha} \left([1 + 2r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2]^{\otimes_{\alpha} 1/2} \otimes_{\alpha} E_{\alpha} \left(i \cdot \arctan_{\alpha} \left(r\sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-1)} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} Ln_{\alpha}(1 + 2r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2) + i \cdot \arctan_{\alpha} \left(r\sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-1)} \right). \quad \text{q.e.d.}$$

Lemma 3.2: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, r is a real number, $|r| < 1$, p is a positive integer, and A is a real matrix, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \cos_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \frac{1}{2} Ln_{\alpha}(1 + 2r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2) \\ & - \sin_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \arctan_{\alpha} \left(r\sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-1)} \right) \\ & = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} \cos_{\alpha}((n+p+1)Ax^{\alpha}) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} & \cos_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \arctan_{\alpha} \left(r \sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-1)} \right) \\ & + \sin_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \frac{1}{2} L n_{\alpha}(1 + 2r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2) \\ & = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} \sin_{\alpha}((n+p+1)Ax^{\alpha}) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Proof Since $|r| < 1$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & [E_{\alpha}(iAx^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} p} \otimes_{\alpha} L n_{\alpha}(1 + r E_{\alpha}(iAx^{\alpha})) \\ & = E_{\alpha}(ipAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} [r E_{\alpha}(iAx^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} (n+1)} \\ & = E_{\alpha}(ipAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} E_{\alpha}(i(n+1)Ax^{\alpha}) \quad (\text{by matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula}) \\ & = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} E_{\alpha}(i(n+p+1)Ax^{\alpha}) \\ & = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} \cos_{\alpha}((n+p+1)Ax^{\alpha}) + i \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} \sin_{\alpha}((n+p+1)Ax^{\alpha}). \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Therefore, by Lemma 3.1

$$\begin{aligned} & \cos_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \frac{1}{2} L n_{\alpha}(1 + 2r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2) \\ & - \sin_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \arctan_{\alpha} \left(r \sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-1)} \right) \\ & = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} \cos_{\alpha}((n+p+1)Ax^{\alpha}), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\arctan_{\alpha} \left(r \sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-1)} \right) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} \sin_{\alpha}((n+p+1)Ax^{\alpha}).$$

q.e.d.

Theorem 3.3: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, r is a real number, $|r| < 1$, m, p are positive integers, and A is a real matrix, then

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}_0D_x^{\alpha})^m \left[\begin{array}{c} \cos_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \frac{1}{2} L n_{\alpha}(1 + 2r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2) \\ - \sin_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \arctan_{\alpha} \left(r \sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-1)} \right) \end{array} \right] \\ & = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} (n+p+1)^m A^m \cos_{\alpha} \left((n+p+1)Ax^{\alpha} + m \cdot \frac{T_{\alpha}}{4} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}_0D_x^{\alpha})^m \left[\begin{array}{c} \cos_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \arctan_{\alpha} \left(r \sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-1)} \right) \\ + \sin_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \frac{1}{2} L n_{\alpha}(1 + 2r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2) \end{array} \right] \\ & = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} (n+p+1)^m A^m \sin_{\alpha} \left((n+p+1)Ax^{\alpha} + m \cdot \frac{T_{\alpha}}{4} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Proof By Lemma 3.2,

$$({}_0D_x^{\alpha})^m \left[\begin{array}{c} \cos_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \frac{1}{2} L n_{\alpha}(1 + 2r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + r^2) \\ - \sin_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \arctan_{\alpha} \left(r \sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} [1 + r \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-1)} \right) \end{array} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} \cos_\alpha((n+p+1)Ax^\alpha) \right] \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\cos_\alpha((n+p+1)Ax^\alpha)] \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} (n+p+1)^m A^m \cos_\alpha \left((n+p+1)Ax^\alpha + m \cdot \frac{T_\alpha}{4} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

On the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned}
&({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m \left[\cos_\alpha(pAx^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha \left(r \sin_\alpha(Ax^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r \cos_\alpha(Ax^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha (-1)} \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \sin_\alpha(pAx^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{Ln}_\alpha(1 + 2r \cos_\alpha(Ax^\alpha) + r^2) \right] \\
&= ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} \sin_\alpha((n+p+1)Ax^\alpha) \right] \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\sin_\alpha((n+p+1)Ax^\alpha)] \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1} r^{n+1} (n+p+1)^m A^m \sin_\alpha \left((n+p+1)Ax^\alpha + m \cdot \frac{T_\alpha}{4} \right). \quad \text{q.e.d.}
\end{aligned}$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on Jumarie's modified R-L fractional derivative and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we can find arbitrary order fractional derivative of two types of matrix fractional functions. In addition, our results are generalizations of traditional calculus results. In the future, we will continue to use Jumarie type of R-L fractional calculus and the new multiplication of fractional analytic functions to solve problems in engineering mathematics and fractional differential equations.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. V. Uchaikin, Fractional Derivatives for Physicists and Engineers, Vol. 1, Background and Theory, Vol. 2, Application. Springer, 2013.
- [2] A. Carpinteri, F. Mainardi, (Eds.), Fractals and fractional calculus in continuum mechanics, Springer, Wien, 1997.
- [3] Hasan, A. Fallahgoul, Sergio M. Focardi and Frank J. Fabozzi, Fractional calculus and fractional processes with applications to financial economics, Academic Press, 2017.
- [4] Mohd. Farman Ali, Manoj Sharma, Renu Jain, An application of fractional calculus in electrical engineering, Advanced Engineering Technology and Application, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 41-45, 2016.
- [5] E. Soczkiewicz, Application of fractional calculus in the theory of viscoelasticity, Molecular and Quantum Acoustics, vol.23, pp. 397-404. 2002.
- [6] V. E. Tarasov, Mathematical economics: application of fractional calculus, Mathematics, vol. 8, no. 5, 660, 2020.
- [7] M. Teodor, Atanacković, Stevan Pilipović, Bogoljub Stanković, Dušan Zorica, Fractional Calculus with Applications in Mechanics: Vibrations and Diffusion Processes, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2014.
- [8] N. Heymans, Dynamic measurements in long-memory materials: fractional calculus evaluation of approach to steady state, Journal of Vibration and Control, vol. 14, no. 9, pp. 1587-1596, 2008.
- [9] T. Das, U. Ghosh, S. Sarkar, and S. Das, Time independent fractional Schrödinger equation for generalized Mie-type potential in higher dimension framed with Jumarie type fractional derivative, Journal of Mathematical Physics, vol. 59, no. 2, 022111, 2018.
- [10] R. Caponetto, G. Dongola, L. Fortuna, I. Petras, Fractional order systems: modeling and control applications, Singapore: World Scientific, 2010.
- [11] C. Cattani, H. M. Srivastava, and X. -J. Yang, (Eds.), Fractional Dynamics, Emerging Science Publishers (De Gruyter Open), Berlin and Warsaw, 2015.

- [12] R. Hilfer (Ed.), Applications of Fractional Calculus in Physics, WSPC, Singapore, 2000.
- [13] F. B. Adda and J. Cresson, Fractional differential equations and the Schrödinger equation, Applied Mathematics and Computation, vol. 161, pp. 323-345, 2005.
- [14] J. T. Machado, Fractional Calculus: Application in Modeling and Control, Springer New York, 2013.
- [15] C. -H. Yu, A study on fractional RLC circuit, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology, vol. 7, no. 8, pp. 3422-3425, 2020.
- [16] C. -H. Yu, A new insight into fractional logistic equation, International Journal of Engineering Research and Reviews, vol. 9, no. 2, pp.13-17, 2021.
- [17] R. L. Magin, Fractional calculus in bioengineering, part 1, Critical Reviews in Biomedical Engineering, vol. 32, no.1, pp.1-104, 2004.
- [18] K. B. Oldham and J. Spanier, The Fractional Calculus, Academic Press, Inc., 1974.
- [19] S. Das, Functional Fractional Calculus, 2nd ed. Springer-Verlag, 2011.
- [20] K. S. Miller, B. Ross, An Introduction to the Fractional Calculus and Fractional Differential Equations, John Wiley & Sons, New York, USA, 1993.
- [21] I. Podlubny, Fractional Differential Equations, Academic Press, San Diego, Calif, USA, 1999.
- [22] K. Diethelm, The Analysis of Fractional Differential Equations, Springer-Verlag, 2010.
- [23] C. -H. Yu, Research on two types of fractional integrals, International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Research, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 33-37, 2022.
- [24] C. -H. Yu, Study of fractional Fourier series expansions of two types of matrix fractional functions, International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 13-17, 2024.
- [25] C. -H. Yu, Fractional partial differential problem of some matrix two-variables fractional functions, International Journal of Mechanical and Industrial Technology, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 6-13, 2024.
- [26] C. -H. Yu, Study of two matrix fractional integrals by using differentiation under fractional integral sign, International Journal of Civil and Structural Engineering Research, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 24-30, 2024.
- [27] C. -H. Yu, Fractional differential problem of two matrix fractional hyperbolic functions, International Journal of Recent Research in Civil and Mechanical Engineering, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1-4, 2024.
- [28] C. -H. Yu, Evaluating fractional derivatives of two types of matrix fractional functions, International Journal of Recent Research in Electrical and Electronics Engineering, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 6-10, 2024.